

Excursus: Maimonides' "*shishim mitzvot hahechrekhiyot*"
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In his widely-read essay "The Status of Women in Halakhic Judaism" (1973), Saul Berman pointed out inconsistencies in the rabbinic exemption of women from time-bound commandments. The inconsistencies are illustrated on the basis of a list of 60 commandments assembled in the 12th century by Maimonides: Women are exempt from 14 of these commandments, of which only 8 are time-bound.¹

These 60 commandments, which are at the core of Berman's argument, are repeated in a separate listing at the end of the compilation of all 248 positive commandments in the *Sefer Hamitzvot*. Maimonides called these separately listed commandments "*shishim mitzvot hahechrekhiyot*" (ששים מצוות ההכרחיות; 60 categorical commandments; derived from the Hebrew הכרחי [necessary]), because under normal circumstances they are fundamentally relevant for every adult Jew,² independent of time and place – in other words, they are some of the most frequently fulfilled legal obligations.³ According to Maimonides, these commandments are distinguishable from commandments that cannot be fulfilled because the necessary prerequisites, such as the existence of the Temple or ownership of property, are missing.⁴

¹ Berman, Saul J. "The Status of Women in Halakhic Judaism." In *Tradition* 14:2 (1973): 5–28, 12; whereas below, the daily priestly blessing is assigned to the category of time-bound mitzvot, Saul Berman considers it a non-time-bound mitzvah (Berman, "The Status of Women," 12; 25; see also Berman, Saul. "Reshut: Individual Discretion in Halakha." In *JOFA Journal* [Winter 2001]: 4–5).

² *Le-chol ish she-hagiya lekalal shanim miyisrael* (לכל איש שהגיע לכלל שנים מישראל; *The Bar Ilan Responsa Project: Global Jewish Database*, Online Electronic Collection [Ramat Gan: Bar Ilan University]; hereinafter *Responsa*); Maimonides' idea of normal circumstances is daily life in a residential area including a house, food, work, and family (*sefer hamitzvot leRambam siyum mitzvot aseh*; *Responsa Maimonides, Sefer Hamitzvot*. Translated by Shraga Silverstein, 2 vols. New York: Moznaim, 1993).

³ *Sefer hamitzvot leRambam siyum mitzvot aseh*.

⁴ 16 of the 21 commandments discussed above are included in the 60 *mitzvot hahechrekhiyot*; however, the following 5 commandments are not in Maimonides' list: redemption of the firstborn, *re'iyah*, returning a lost object, releasing the mother bird, and *hakhel*; on the redemption of the firstborn see Rhein, Valérie. "Toralesung und die Frau: ein rabbinisches Dilemma." In *Lectio Difficilior* 1 (2014), 62 p., accessed 26 July 2020, www.lectio.unibe.ch/14_1/inhalt_d.htm, 57, footnote 162.

In the list of the 60 commandments, Maimonides referred 14 times to the non-obligation of women:⁵ He used the expression אין הנשים חייבות בה (women are not obligated) 11 times;⁶ the expression מיוחדת בזכרים (specifically for males) twice⁷ and the expression מיוחדת בזכרי כהונה (specifically for male priests) once.⁸ In sum, he stated explicitly that 46 of the 60 *mitzvot hahechrekhiyot* are incumbent on women as well as on men and that women are not obligated to 14 of the 60.⁹

Both an examination of the addressees of the Torah verses underlying the *shishim mitzvot hahechrekhiyot*¹⁰ as well as an examination of Maimonides' classification of these commandments with regard to men and women – which is based on tannaitic and amoraic literature – reveals parallels to the aforementioned observations concerning the 21 commandments in the tractates Qiddushin and Berakhot. More than three-fourths of these 60 commandments (47, to be exact) are based on Torah verses that address Israel in one way or another: 22 address *yisrael*,¹¹ 17 address *beni yisrael*,¹² and 4 each address *kol-adat yisrael*¹³ and *kol-adat beni-yisrael*.¹⁴ A total of 5 commandments address the people (*am*),¹⁵ whereas 8 additional commandments – somewhat more than one-sixth – address other persons or

⁵ In contrast to his comments on the 60 *mitzvot hahechrekhiyot*, Maimonides usually does not explain women's non-obligation in the Sefer Hamitzvot; see Fixler, Dror. "patur nashim mimitzvot aseh she hazman gramam bemischnat haRambam." In *Sinai* 131 (2003): 41–53 (Hebrew).

⁶ Commandments P 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 18, 161, 168, 169, 170, and 212.

⁷ Commandments P 214 and 215.

⁸ Commandment P 26; sefer hamitzvot leRambam siyum mitzvot aseh.

⁹ See tables 3a–c below. Maimonides illustrated these 3 numbers with biblical verses: Song 6:8: "There are sixty queens (...);" Deuteronomy 32:36: the term יד (hand) correlates to the numerical value 14; Zechariah 9:11: the term בדם (because of the blood [of your covenant]) correlates to the numerical value 46; see also Maimonides, *Sefer (vol. I)*, 241.

¹⁰ The 60 commandments, the Torah verses on which they are based, as well as their addressees are listed in table 1 below.

¹¹ All 22 commandments are included in Moses' second speech (Deuteronomy 4:44–28:69; see Tigay, Jeffrey H. *Deuteronomy: The JPS Torah Commentary*. Philadelphia: The Jewish Publication Society, 1996, 58), which addresses *yisrael* (Sefer Hamitzvot, commandments P 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 19, 54, 94, 143, 146, 150, 172, 184, 195, 207, 213, 214).

¹² Commandments P 5, 14, 73, 147, 149, 152, 154, 161, 162, 163, 166, 167, 168, 169, 170, 175, 197.

¹³ Commandments P 156, 158, 159, 160.

¹⁴ Commandments P 206, 208, 209, 211.

¹⁵ Commandments P 1, 8, 155, 157, 210.

groups.¹⁶ Again, one-third of the listed commandments conflict with the principle handed down in m. Qiddushin 1:7, according to which women are obligated to non-time-bound positive commandments and are exempt from time-bound positive commandments: Of the 14 mitzvot to which Maimonides does not obligate them, 5 are non-time-bound,¹⁷ and of the 46 mitzvot to which he obligates women, 15 are time-bound.¹⁸

As stated above, the *tannaim* and *amoraim* frequently do not discuss explicitly the obligation or non-obligation of women with regard to time-bound commandments.¹⁹ From Maimonides' explicit statements in the list that 14 of the 60 *mitzvot hahechrekhivot* are not binding on women, however, their obligation to the other 46 can be inferred. In any case, this is stated explicitly in his comments following the list. Accordingly, women are obligated to 15 (almost two-thirds) of the 24 time-bound commandments included in the 60. Of these, 8 (more than half) involve commandments to rest; the rabbinic obligation of women to these commandments complements their obligation to the corresponding proscriptions.²⁰ Regardless, the inconsistencies in the principle of exempting women from *mitzvot aseh she hazman graman* can be seen in the following: Maimonides' obligation of women to the vast majority of the 24 listed time-bound commandments; the large portion of commandments (20 of 60) that contradict the rabbinic principle;²¹ and the parallels to the above observations regarding the 21 commandments from tractates Qiddushin and Berakhot.

¹⁶ Commandments P 9, 18, 26, 32, 164, 165, 212, 215.

¹⁷ Maimonides lists *tefillin* for head and hand as two independent mitzvot (P 12 and 13); in the following, references to *tefillin* in the context of the *shishim mitzvot hahechrekhivot* will also do so. For the the daily priestly blessing see footnote 1 above.

¹⁸ See table 2 below.

¹⁹ In tannaitic or amoraic literature there is, for example, no indication regarding women's exemption from or obligation to the mitzvah to recount the Exodus from Egypt (Exodus 13:8; P 157; in m. Pesahim 10:5 the obligation is imposed on everyone [*adam*]). Only in post-Talmudic literature is this mitzvah explicitly imposed on women (see e.g. Shulhan Arukh, OH 472:14 [*Responsa*]; Benovitz, Moshe. "Time-triggered Positive Commandments as Conversation Pieces." In *HUCA* 78 [2007]: 45–90, 49; Ellinson, Getsel. "Serving the Creator: A Guide to the Rabbinic Sources." In *Woman and the Mitzvot*, vol. 1. Jerusalem: World Zionist Organization, 1986, 64; 113; 194; 199f.; 277; but see Hauptman, Judith. "From the Kitchen to the Dining Room: Women and Ritual Activities in Tractate Pesahim." In *A Feminist Commentary on the Babylonian Talmud: Introduction and Studies*, eds. Tal Ilan et al. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2007, 109–126, 118, on b. Pesahim 116a).

²⁰ The prescription to rest on the first day of *pesah* (Exodus 12:16; Leviticus 23:7; P160), for example, is based on an analogy to the proscription to work on the first day of *pesah* (*ibid.*; N 323); for more examples see Rhein, Valérie. "Law, Hierarchy, and Gender. Reflections on the Exemption of Women from Time-Bound Commandments." In *Judaica. Neue digitale Folge* 1 (2020), <https://bop.unibe.ch/judaica>, footnote 92.

²¹ See table 2 below.

In sum, the rabbinic assignment of commandments to men and women takes place, as a rule, independently of the groups addressed by the underlying Torah verses. The inconsistency of m. Qiddushin 1:7, according to which women are exempt from time-bound commandments, has been shown: Both in the tractates Qiddushin and Berakhot, where the discussion takes place, and in Maimonides' *shishim mitzvot hahechrekhivot*, one-third of the listed commandments contradict the principle.

Maimonides' "*shishim mitzvot hahechrekhivot*" with Torah verses and groups of addressees

- Table 1: The 60 commandments with Torah verses and groups of addressees (page 5)
- Table 2: 20 Commandments that deviate from the principles of m. Qiddushin 1:7 (page 16)
- Tables 3a, 3b, 3c: 14 Commandments to which women are not obligated (pages 17–19)

Legend left column

Non-time-bound commandment: woman obligated (31)

Time-bound commandment: woman not obligated (9)

Time-bound commandment: woman obligated (15)

Non-time-bound commandment: woman not obligated (5)

Numeration Sefer Hamitzvot

Numeration Sefer Hahinukh

⌚ time-bound

⊕ non-time-bound

Maimonides' phrasing in the "*shishim mitzvot hahechrekhivot*" list on women's non-obligation (in Hebrew)

Legend middle column

[] = Verses preceding or following the relevant verse will appear in square brackets with a smaller font.

Legend right column

The groups of addressees most frequently listed in the context of mitzvot are highlighted in color:

Israel (ישראל)

People of Israel (בני ישראל)

People (עם)

Other (groups of) addressees

[] = Verses preceding or following the relevant verse will appear in square brackets with a smaller font.

Biblical quotes are based on *The New Oxford Annotated Bible: New Revised Standard Version, With The Apocrypha*, eds. Michael D. Coogan et al. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010; *emphasis vr*. References to Sefer Hahinukh are based on *Sefer haHinnuch: The Book of (Mitzvah) Education*, Ascribed to Rabbi Aaron haLévi of Barcelona, With a Translation and Notes by Charles Wengrov, 5 vols. Jerusalem: Feldheim, 1978–1989.

Table 1: The 60 Commandments with Torah Verses and Groups of Addressees

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
To believe in God ⊕ P 1 [25]	[20:1: Then God spoke all these words:] Exod 20:2: I am the Lord your God, who brought you out of the land of Egypt, out of the house of slavery.	People; Exod 19:25: So Moses went down to the people and told them.
The unity of God ⊕ P 2 [417]	Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: The Lord is our God, the Lord alone.	Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]
To love God ⊕ P 3 [418]	Deut 6:5: You shall love the Lord your God with all your heart, and with all your soul, and with all your might.	Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]
To fear God ⊕ P 4 [432]	Deut 6:13: The Lord your God you shall fear; him you shall serve, and by his name alone you shall swear.	Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]
To serve God ⊕ * P 5 [433] * The time-boundness of this commandment has been subject of controversy among the rabbis (see Ellinson 1986, 171f.)	Exod 23:25: You shall worship the Lord your God, and I will bless your bread and your water; and I will take sickness away from among you. (<i>Sefer Hamitzvot</i>) Deut 10:20: You shall fear the Lord your God; him alone you shall worship; to him you shall hold fast, and by his name you shall swear. (<i>Sefer Hahinukh</i>) Maimonides points out to repetitions of the commandment, for example in Deut 6:13, 11:13 and 13:5 (Israel in Deut 5:1).	People of Israel; Exod 20:19/22:* The Lord said to Moses: Thus you shall say to the people of Israel: (...). [Speech ends in Exod 23:33.] [Exod 22:30/31*: You shall be people consecrated (אנשי-קדש) to me.] Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...). * (different numeration depending on bible edition)

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>To cleave to God ⊕ P 6 [434]</p>	<p>Deut 11:22: If you diligently observe this entire commandment that I am commanding you, loving the Lord your God, walking in all his ways, and holding fast to him, [11:23: then the Lord will drive out all these nations before you, and you will dispossess nations larger and mightier than yourselves].</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Deut 10:20: You shall fear the Lord your God; him alone you shall worship; to him you shall hold fast (...); (Israel in Deut 5:1).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To swear in God's name when swearing is necessary ⊕ P 7 [435]</p>	<p>Deut 10:20: You shall fear the Lord your God; him alone you shall worship; to him you shall hold fast, and by his name you shall swear.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>Walking in God's ways ⊕ P 8 [611]</p>	<p>Deut 28:9: The Lord will establish you as his holy people, as he has sworn to you, if you keep the commandments of the Lord your God and walk in his ways.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to repetitions of the commandment, for example in Deut 11:22 and 13:5 (Israel in Deut 5:1). The commandment is also repeated in Deut 10:12: (...) what does the Lord your God require of you? (...) to walk in all his ways (...).</p>	<p>People; Deut 27:11: The same day Moses charged the people as follows: (...). [Speech ends in Deut 28:68.]</p>
<p>To sanctify God's name ⊕ P 9 [296]</p>	<p>Lev 22:32: You shall not profane my holy name, that I may be sanctified among the people of Israel: I am the Lord; I sanctify you (...).</p>	<p>Moses; Lev 22:26: The Lord spoke to Moses: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 22:33.] Moses: Aaron: Aaron and his sons: People of Israel; Lev 22:17–18: The Lord spoke to Moses, saying: Speak to Aaron and his sons and all the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Lev 22:25.]</p>
<p>Shema ⌚ P 10 [420] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Deut 6:7: Recite them to your children (לבניך) and talk about them [these words; Deut 6:6] when you are at home and when you are away, when you lie down and when you rise.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובניך ובני-בניך)]</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>Talmud torah ⊕ P 11 [419] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Deut 6:7: Recite them to your children (לבניך) and talk about them [these words; Deut 6:6] when you are at home and when you are away, when you lie down and when you rise.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Deut 31:12: (...) so that they may hear and learn (...); (people in Deut 31:12).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]</p>
<p>Tefillin for the head ⌚ P 12 [422] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Deut 6:8: Bind them [these words; Deut 6:6] as a sign on your hand, fix them as an emblem <i>on your forehead</i> (...).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]</p>
<p>Tefillin for the hand ⌚ P 13 [421] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Deut 6:8: Bind them [these words; Deut 6:6] as a sign <i>on your hand</i>, fix them as an emblem on your forehead (...).</p> <p>Maimonides points out to three repetitions of the commandment in Exod 13:9 and 13:16 (people in Exod 13:3) and in Deut 11:18 (Israel in Deut 5:1).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]</p>
<p>Tzitzit ⌚ P 14 [386] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Num 15:38: Speak to the people of Israel and tell them to make fringes on the corners of their garments throughout their generations and to put a blue cord on the fringe at each corner.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Num 15:38: Speak to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Num 15:41.]</p>
<p>Mezuzah ⊕ P 15 [423]</p>	<p>Deut 6:9: (...) and write them [these words; Deut 6:6] on the doorposts of your house and on your gates.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Deut 11:20: Write them on the doorposts of your house and on your gates (Israel in Deut 5:1).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]</p>
<p>To write (or have written) a Torah scroll of one's own ⊕ P 18 [613] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Deut 31:19: Now therefore write [Moses; Deut 31:14] this song, and teach it to the people of Israel (...). [31:22: That very day Moses wrote this song and taught it to the people of Israel.]</p>	<p>Moses; Deut 31:16: The Lord said to Moses: "Soon you will lie down with your ancestors (...)." [Speech ends in Deut 31:21.] Group of addressees in the context: people of Israel; Deut 31:19 ([...] teach it to the people of Israel) and 31:22: ([...] Moses [...] taught it to the people of Israel).</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p><i>Birkat hamazon</i> ⊕ P 19 [430]</p>	<p>Deut 8:10: You shall eat your fill and bless the Lord your God for the good land that he has given you.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך ובן-בנך)]</p>
<p>Daily priestly blessing ⌚ P 26 [378] מייוחדת בזכרי כהונה</p>	<p>[Num 6:22: The Lord spoke to Moses, saying:] Num 6:23/6:27: Speak to Aaron and his sons: Thus you shall bless the people of Israel: You shall say to them (...). So they shall put my name on the people of Israel, and I will bless them.</p>	<p>Moses; Num 6:22: The Lord spoke to Moses (...). [Speech ends in Num 6:27.] Aaron and his sons; Num 6:23: Speak to Aaron and his sons (...). People of Israel; Num 6:23: (...) Thus you shall bless the people of Israel (...); Num 6: 27: So they shall put my name on the people of Israel, and I will bless them.</p>
<p>To honour the descendants of Aaron ⊕ P 32 [269]</p>	<p>Lev 21:8: And you shall treat them as holy, since they offer the food of your God; they shall be holy to you, for the Lord, I who sanctify you, am holy.</p>	<p>Moses; priests/descendants of Aaron; Lev 21:1: The Lord said to Moses: Speak to the priests, the sons of Aaron, and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 21:15.]</p>
<p>To rejoice on the festivals ⌚ P 54 [488]</p>	<p>Deut 16:14: Rejoice during your festival, you and your sons and your daughters, your male and female slaves, as well as the Levites, the strangers, the orphans, and the widows resident in your towns. [Deut 16:1f.: Pesach; 16:10f.: Shavuot; 16:13: Sukkot]</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To confess sins (on yom kippur) ⌚ P 73 [364]</p>	<p>[Num 5:5: The Lord spoke to Moses, saying:] Num 5:6–7: Speak to the people of Israel: When a man or a woman wrongs another, breaking faith with the Lord, that person incurs guilt and shall confess the sin that has been committed. The person shall make full restitution for the wrong, adding one-fifth to it, and giving it to the one who was wronged.</p>	<p>Moses; Num 5:5: The Lord spoke to Moses (...); people of Israel, man or woman; Num 5:6: Speak to the people of Israel: When a man or a woman (...). [Speech ends in Num 5:10.]</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>To fulfill what one takes upon oneself by word ⊕ P 94 [575]</p>	<p>[Deut 23:22:* But if you refrain from vowing, you will not incur guilt.] Deut 23:23:* Whatever your lips utter you must diligently perform, just as you have freely vowed to the Lord your God with your own mouth.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Num 30:2:* When a man (איש) makes a vow to the Lord, or swears an oath to bind himself by a pledge, he shall not break this word; he shall do according to all that proceeds out of his mouth. (people of Israel/man in Num 30:1–2). [Num 30:3:* When a woman makes a vow to the Lord, or binds herself by a pledge, while within her father's house, in her youth (...).]</p> <p>* (different numeration depending on bible edition)</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To give shoulder, jowls, and stomach of slaughtered animals to the priest ⊕ P 143 [506]</p>	<p>Deut 18:3: This shall be the priests' due from the people, from those offering a sacrifice, whether an ox or a sheep: They shall give to the priest the shoulder, the two jowls, and the stomach.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To ritually slaughter (an animal before eating from it) ⊕ P 146 [451]</p>	<p>Deut 12:21: If the place where the Lord your God will choose to put his name is too far from you, and you slaughter a I have commanded you any of your herd or flock that the Lord has given you, then you may eat within your towns whenever you desire.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To cover the blood of an animal after slaughtering ⊕ P 147 [187]</p>	<p>Lev 17:13: And anyone (איש איש) of the people of Israel, or of the aliens who reside among them, who hunts down an animal or bird that may be eaten shall pour out its blood and cover it with earth.</p>	<p>Aaron, Aaron's sons, all the people of Israel; Lev 17:2: Speak to Aaron and his sons and to all the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in 17:16.] Anyone (איש איש), people of Israel, alien; Lev 17:13: And anyone (איש איש) of the people of Israel, or of the aliens who reside among them (...).</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>To examine animals for signs (of cleanness)</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>P 149 [153]</p>	<p>Lev 11:2–3: Speak [Moses and Aaron; Lev 11:1] to the people of Israel, saying: From among all the land animals, these are the creatures that you may eat. Any animal that has divided hoofs and is cleft-footed and chews the cud – such you may eat.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 11:2: Speak [Moses and Aaron] to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in 11:47.]</p>
<p>To examine birds for signs (of cleanness)</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>P 150 [470]</p>	<p>Deut 14:11: You may eat any clean birds.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To examine fish for signs (of cleanness)</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>P 152 [155]</p>	<p>Lev 11:9: These you may eat, of all that are in the waters. Everything in the waters that has fins and scales, whether in the seas or in the streams – such you may eat.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 11:2: Speak [Moses and Aaron] to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Lev 11:47.]</p>
<p>To rest on Shabbat</p> <p>🕒</p> <p>P 154 [85]</p>	<p>Exod 23:12: Six days you shall do your work, but on the seventh day you shall rest, so that your ox and your donkey may have relief, and your homeborn slave and the resident alien may be refreshed.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Exod 20:22:* The Lord said to Moses: Thus you shall say to the people of Israel: (...). [Speech ends in Exod 23:33.] [Exod 22:31*: You shall be people consecrated (אנשי-קדש) to me.]</p> <p>* (different numeration depending on bible edition)</p>
<p>To sanctify the day</p> <p>🕒</p> <p>P 155 [31]</p>	<p>Exod 20:8: Remember the sabbath day, and keep it holy.</p>	<p>People; Exod 19:25: So Moses went down to the people and told them.</p>
<p>To remove chametz (before pesah)</p> <p>🕒</p> <p>P 156 [9]</p>	<p>Exod 12:15: Seven days you shall eat unleavened bread; on the first day you shall remove leaven from your houses, for whoever eats leavened bread from the first day until the seventh day shall be cut off from Israel.</p>	<p>The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3: (...) Tell [Moses and Aaron; Exod 12:1] the whole congregation of Israel (...). [Speech Exod 12:2–12:20]</p>
<p>To recount the Exodus from Egypt</p> <p>🕒</p> <p>P 157 [21]</p>	<p>Exod 13:8: You shall tell your child (לבניך) on that day, 'It is because of what the Lord did for me when I came out of Egypt.'</p>	<p>People; Exod 13:3: Moses said to the people: "Remember this day (...)." [Speech ends in Exod 13:16.]</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>Matzah (at the seder) 🕒 P 158 [10]</p>	<p>Exod 12:18: In the first month, from the evening of the fourteenth day until the evening of the twenty-first day, you shall eat unleavened bread.</p>	<p>The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3: (...) Tell [Moses and Aaron; Exod 12:1] the whole congregation of Israel (...). [Speech Exod 12:2–12:20]</p>
<p>To rest on the first day of pesah 🕒 P 159 [297]</p>	<p>Exod 12:16: On the first day you shall hold a solemn assembly (...).</p>	<p>The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3: (...) Tell [Moses and Aaron; Exod 12:1] the whole congregation of Israel (...). [Speech Exod 12:2–12:20]</p>
<p>To rest on the seventh day of pesah 🕒 P 160 [300]</p>	<p>Exod 12:16: (...) and on the seventh day [you shall hold] a solemn assembly. [No work shall be done on those days; only what everyone must eat, that alone may be prepared by you.]</p>	<p>The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3: (...) Tell [Moses and Aaron; Exod 12:1] the whole congregation of Israel (...). [Speech Exod 12:2–12:20]</p>
<p>To count the omer (between pesah and shavuot) 🕒 P 161 [306] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Lev 23:15–16: And from the day after the sabbath, from the day on which you bring the sheaf of the elevation offering, you shall count off seven weeks; they shall be complete. You shall count until the day after the seventh sabbath, fifty days; then you shall present an offering of new grain to the Lord.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Deut 16:9: You shall count seven weeks (...). (Israel in Deut 5:1)</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:10: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:9] to the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:22.]</p>
<p>To rest on shavuot 🕒 P 162 [308]</p>	<p>Lev 23:21: On that same day you shall make proclamation; you shall hold a holy convocation; you shall not work at your occupations. This is a statute forever in all your settlements throughout your generations.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:10: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:9] to the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:22.]</p>
<p>To rest on rosh hashanah 🕒 P 163 [310]</p>	<p>Lev 23:24: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:23] to the people of Israel, saying: In the seventh month, on the first day of the month, you shall observe a day of complete rest, a holy convocation commemorated with trumpet blasts.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:24: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:23] to the people of Israel, saying: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:25.]</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>To fast on yom kippur 🕒 P 164 [313]</p>	<p>Lev 16:29: This shall be a statute to your forever: In the seventh month, on the tenth day of the month, you shall deny yourselves, and shall do not work, neither the citizen nor the alien who resides among you.</p>	<p>Moses; Aaron; Lev 16:2: The Lord said to Moses: Tell your brother Aaron (...). [Speech ends in Lev 16:34.] The citizen (האזרח) and the alien (הגֵּר); Lev 16:29: (...) neither the citizen nor the alien who resides among you.</p>
<p>To rest on yom kippur 🕒 P 165 [317]</p>	<p>Lev 16:31: It is a sabbath of complete rest to you, and you shall deny yourselves; it is a statute forever.</p>	<p>Moses; Aaron; Lev 16:2: The Lord said to Moses: Tell your brother Aaron (...). [Speech ends in Lev 16:34.] The citizen (האזרח) and the alien (הגֵּר); Lev 16:29: (...) neither the citizen nor the alien who resides among you.</p>
<p>To rest on the first day of sukkot 🕒 P 166 [318]</p>	<p>Lev 23:35: The first day [of the festival of booths; Lev 23:34] shall be a holy convocation; you shall not work at your occupations.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:34: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:33] to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:43.]</p>
<p>To rest on the eighth day of sukkot 🕒 P 167 [321]</p>	<p>Lev 23:36: (...) on the eighth day [of the festival of booths; Lev 23:34] you shall observe a holy convocation (...); you shall not work at your occupations.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:34: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:33] to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:43.]</p>
<p>Sukkah 🕒 P 168 [325] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Lev 23:42: You shall live in booths for seven days; all that are citizens in Israel shall live in booths, [23:43] so that your generations may know that I made the people of Israel live in booths when I brought them out of the land of Egypt: I am the Lord your God.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:34: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:33] to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:43.] All that are citizens (כל-האזרח); Lev 23:42: (...) all that are citizens in Israel (...).</p>
<p>Lulav 🕒 P 169 [324] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Lev 23:40: On the first day you shall take the fruit of majestic trees, branches of palm trees, boughs of leafy trees, and willows of the brook; and you shall rejoice before the Lord your God for seven days.</p>	<p>People of Israel ; Lev 23:34: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:33] to the people of Israel (...). [Speech ends in Lev 23:43.]</p>
<p>Shofar 🕒 P 170 [405] אין הנשים חייבות בה</p>	<p>Num 29:1: On the first day of the seventh month you shall have a holy convocation; you shall not work at your occupations. It is a day for you to blow the trumpets.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Num 28:2: Command [Moses; Num 28:1] the people of Israel, and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Num 29:39.]</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>To listen to the prophets ⊕ P 172 [516]</p>	<p>Deut 18:15: The Lord your God will raise up for you a prophet like me [Moses] from among your own people (מֵאַחֶיךָ); you shall heed such a prophet.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To follow the majority (in case of disagreement) ⊕ P 175 [78]</p>	<p>Exod 23:2: You shall not follow a majority in wrongdoing; when you bear witness in lawsuit, you shall not side with the majority so as to pervert justice.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Exod 20:22:* The Lord said to Moses: Thus you shall say to the people of Israel: (...). [Speech ends in Exod 23:33.] [Exod 22:31*: You shall be people consecrated (שְׂמֵךְ-אֱנִשִּׁי) to me.]</p> <p>* (different numeration depending on bible edition)</p>
<p>To make a guard rail around flat roofs ⊕ P 184 [546]</p>	<p>Deut 22:8: When you build a new house, you shall make a parapet for your roof; otherwise you might have bloodguilt on your house, if anyone should fall from it.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>Tzedakah (charity) ⊕ P 195 [479]</p>	<p>Deut 15:7–8; 11 If there is among you anyone [אֶחָד] in need, a member of your community in any of your towns within the land that the Lord your God is giving you, do not be hard-hearted or tight-fisted toward your needy neighbor [מֵאַחֶיךָ]. You should rather open your hand, willingly lending enough to meet the need, whatever it may be. (...) Since there will never cease to be some in need on the earth, I therefore command you, “Open your hand to the poor and needy neighbor [לְאֶחָד] in your land.”</p> <p>Maimonides points out to repetitions of the commandment, for example in Lev 25:35 [people of Israel in Lev 25:2], phrased in the second person plural as well (אַתָּם).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
<p>To lend to the poor ⊕ P 197 [66]</p>	<p>Exod 22:25:* If you lend money to my people, to the poor among you, you shall not deal with them as a creditor; you shall not exact interest from them.</p> <p>* (different numeration depending on bible edition)</p>	<p>People of Israel; Exod 20:22:* The Lord said to Moses: Thus you shall say to the people of Israel: (...). [Speech ends in Exod 23:33.] [Exod 22:31*: You shall be people consecrated (אנשי-קדש) to me.]</p> <p>* (different numeration depending on bible edition)</p>
<p>To love one another ⊕ P 206 [243]</p>	<p>Lev 19:18: (...) but you shall love your neighbor as yourself (...).</p>	<p>All the congregation of the people of Israel; Lev 19:2: Speak [Moses; Lev 19:1] to all the congregation of the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 19:37.]</p>
<p>To love proselytes ⊕ P 207 [431]</p>	<p>Deut 10:19: You shall also love the stranger (הגר), for you were strangers in the land of Egypt.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>
<p>To ensure that weights, balances, and measures are accurate ⊕ P 208 [259]</p>	<p>Lev 19:36: You shall have honest balances, honest weights, an honest epha, and an honest hin (...).</p>	<p>All the congregation of the people of Israel; Lev 19:2: Speak [Moses; Lev 19:1] to all the congregation of the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 19:37.]</p>
<p>To honor the sages ⊕ P 209 [257]</p>	<p>Lev 19:32: You shall rise before the aged, and defer to the old (...).</p>	<p>All the congregation of the people of Israel; Lev 19:2: Speak [Moses; Lev 19:1] to all the congregation of the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 19:37.]</p>
<p>To honor father and mother ⊕ P 210 [33]</p>	<p>Exod 20:12: Honor your father and your mother, so that your days may be long in the land that the Lord your God is giving you.</p> <p>Deut 5:16: Honor your father and your mother, as the Lord your God commanded you, so that your days may be long and that it may go well with you in the land that the Lord your God is giving you.</p>	<p>People; Exod 19:25: So Moses went down to the people and told them.</p> <p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/verse
To fear father and mother ⊕ P 211 [212]	Lev 19:3: You shall each (איש) revere your mother and father, and you shall keep my sabbaths: I am the Lord your God.	All the congregation of the people of Israel ; Lev 19:2: Speak [Moses; Lev 19:1] to all the congregation of the people of Israel and say to them: (...). [Speech ends in Lev 19:37.]
Procreation ⊕ P 212 [1] אין הנשים חייבות בה	Gen 1:28: God blessed them [male and female (זכר ונקבה)]; Gen 1:27: and God said to them: “Be fruitful and multiply and fill the earth and subdue it (...).”	Humankind (אדם) (...): male and female; Gen 1:27: So God created humankind in his image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.
To marry a wife ⊕ P 213 [552]	Deut 24:1: Suppose a man enters into marriage with a woman (...).	Israel ; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).
The bridegroom devotes himself to his wife for a year ⊕ P 214 [582] מיוחדת בזכרים	Deut 24:5: When a man is newly married, he shall not go out with the army or be charged with any related duty. He shall be free at home one year, to be happy with the wife whom he has married.	Israel ; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). [Speech ends in Deut 26:19]; Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).
To circumcise (a son) ⊕* P 215 [2] מיוחדת בזכרים	Gen 17:10/17:14: [17:10] “This is my covenant, which you shall keep, between me and you and your offspring after you: Every male among you shall be circumcised. (...) [17:14] Any uncircumcised male who is not circumcised in the flesh of his foreskin shall be cut off from his people; he has broken my covenant.” In the Sefer Hahinukh there is a reference to a repetition of the commandment in Lev 12:3: On the eighth day the flesh of his foreskin shall be circumcised (people of Israel in Lev 12:1).	Abraham and his offspring ; Gen 17:9: God said to Abraham, “As for you, you shall keep my covenant, you and your offspring after you throughout their generations.” [Speech ends in Gen 17:14.]

* There is a discussion in bYevamot 72a–b as to whether circumcision might be time-bound; see also Tosafot on b. Qiddushin 29a (*Bar Ilan Responsa Project*). But in general, circumcision is considered to be non-time-bound (see Alexander, Elizabeth Shanks. *Gender and Timebound Commandments in Judaism*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2013, 12 [footnote 12]). Moreover, in tannaic and amoraic literature circumcision is mentioned as an example of commandments to which a father, unlike a mother, is obligated vis-à-vis a son (t. Qiddushin 1:11; b. Qiddushin 29a; y. Qiddushin 1:7 [61a], 18).

Table 2: 20 Commandments that deviate from the principles of m. Qiddushin 1:7

Commandment Time-bound: woman obligated Non-time-bound: woman not obligated Numeration Sefer Hamitzvot and [Sefer Hahinukh]	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/ verse Israel People of Israel People Other
To rejoice on the festivals ⌚ P 54 [488]	Deut 16:14	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4; 10:12
To confess sins (on yom kippur) ⌚ P 73 [364]	Num 5:6–7	Moses; Num 5:5; People of Israel: man or woman; Num 5:6
To rest on Shabbat ⌚ P 154 [85]	Exod 23:12	People of Israel; Exod 20:19
To sanctify the day ⌚ P 155 [31]	Exod 20:8	People; Exod 19:25
To remove chametz (before pesah) ⌚ P 156 [9]	Exod 12:15	The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3
To recount the Exodus from Egypt ⌚ P 157 [21]	Exod 13:8	People; Exod 13:3
Matzah ⌚ P 158 [10]	Exod 12:18	The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3
To rest on the first day of pesah ⌚ P 159 [297]	Exod 12:16	The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3
To rest on the seventh day of pesah ⌚ P 160 [300]	Exod 12:16	The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3
To rest on shavuot ⌚ P 162 [308]	Lev 23:21	People of Israel; Lev 23:10
To rest on rosh hashanah ⌚ P 163 [310]	Lev 23:24	People of Israel; Lev 23:24
To fast on yom kippur ⌚ P 164 [313]	Lev 16:29 and 16:31	Moses; Aaron; Lev 16:2 The citizen and the alien; Lev 16:29
To rest on yom kippur ⌚ P 165 [317]	Lev 16:31	Moses; Aaron; Lev 16:2 The citizen and the alien; Lev 16:29

To rest on the first day of <i>sukkot</i> ⌚ P 166 [318]	Lev 23:35	People of Israel; Lev 23:34
To rest on the eighth day of <i>sukkot</i> ⌚ P 167 [321]	Lev 23:36	People of Israel; Lev 23:34
Talmud torah ⊕ P 11 [419]	Deut 6:7	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4
To write (or have written) a Torah scroll of one's own ⊕ P 18 [613]	Deut 31:19	Moses; Deut 31:16
Procreation ⊕ P 212 [1]	Gen 1:28	Humankind (אדם) (...): male and female; Gen 1:27
The bridegroom devotes himself to his wife for a year ⊕ P 214 [582]	Deut 24:5	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4, 10:12 et al.
To circumcise (a son) ⊕ P 215 [2]	Gen 17:10	Abraham and his offspring; Gen 17:9–10

Tables 3a, 3b, 3c: 14 Commandments to which women are not obligated

Table 3a: “women are not obligated” (אין הנשים חייבות בה)

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based	Groups of addressees/ verse
Shema ⌚ P 10 [420]	Deut 6:7	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4
Talmud torah ⊕ P 11 [419]	Deut 6:7	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4
Tefillin for the head ⌚ P 12 [422]	Deut 6:8	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4
Tefillin for the hand ⌚ P 13 [421]	Deut 6:8 See also Exod 13:9 and 13:16 (people in Exod 13:3) and Deut 11:18 (Israel in Deut 10:12).	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4

Tzitzit ⌚ P 14 [386]	Num 15:38	People of Israel; Num 15:38
To write (or have written) a Torah scroll of one's own ⊕ P 18 [613]	Deut 31:19	Moses; Deut 31:16
To count the omer ⌚ P 161 [306]	Lev 23:15–16	People of Israel; Lev 23:10
Sukkah ⌚ P 168 [325]	Lev 23:42	People of Israel; Lev 23:34 All that are citizens; Lev 23:42
Lulav ⌚ P 169 [324]	Lev 23:40	People of Israel; Lev 23:34
Shofar ⌚ P 170 [405]	Num 29:1	People of Israel; Num 28:2
Procreation ⊕ P 212 [1]	Gen 1:28	Humankind (אדם) (...): male and female; Gen 1:27

Table 3b: “specifically for males” (מיוחדת בזכרים)

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based	Groups of addressees/ verse
The bridegroom devotes himself to his wife for a year ⊕ P 214 [582]	Deut 24:5	Israel; Deut 5:1 (all Israel); Deut 6:4, 10:12 et al.
To circumcise (a son) ⊕ P 215 [2]	Gen 17:10	Abraham and his offspring; Gen 17:9–10:

Table 3c: “specifically for male priests” (מיוחדת בזכרי כהונה)

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based	Groups of addressees/ verse
<p>Daily priestly blessing</p> <p>🕒</p> <p>P 26 [378]</p>	<p>Num 6:23–27</p>	<p>Moses; Num 6:22</p> <p>Aaron and his sons; Num 6:23</p> <p>blessing the people of Israel;</p> <p>Num 6:23</p>